

ToLCNDV-Spain is not transmitted by *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* and is inefficiently transmitted by *Bemisia tabaci* MED between zucchini and the wild cucurbit *Ecballium elaterium*

ToLCNDV-Spain, Begomoviruses, Whiteflies, Transmission

Spain and Italy

Begomoviruses constitute a successful group of emerging plant viruses threatening vegetable, root and fiber crops worldwide that are transmitted in nature by whiteflies of the *Bemisia tabaci* complex.

Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus is a paradigmatic example of a *begomovirus* that has recently emerged in Mediterranean countries after movement from its original location in the Indian subcontinent.

The Mediterranean isolates of this virus belong to a novel strain, named "*Spain strain*", which infects **zucchini and other cucurbits** but is poorly adapted to tomato.

This study aimed to understand how the New Delhi tomato leaf curl virus is transmitted by whiteflies. Unlike a previous study, the Mediterranean virus strain is not transmitted by the greenhouse whitefly. The most common whitefly is also not an efficient vector between zucchini plants and *Ecballium elaterium*. It suggests that this wild plant, although infected, may not be significant in the virus's spread.

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Begomoviruses: what is the secret(s) of their success?

Begomoviruses, Bemisia tabaci, emergent diseases, plant viruses, recombination

Spain

Begomovirus

Begomoviruses constitute an extremely successful group of emerging plant viruses transmitted by whiteflies of the *Bemisia tabaci* complex.

Hosts include important vegetable, root, and fiber crops grown in the tropics and subtropics.

Success Factors

- 1 Predisposition to recombine their genomes
- 2 Interaction with DNA satellites recruited throughout their evolution
- 3 Presence of wild plants as a virus reservoir and a source of speciation
- 4 Me polyphagia and continuous movement of the insect vectors to temperate regions.

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These features as well as some controversial issues (replication in the insect vector, putative seed transmission, transmission by insects other than *B. tabaci*, and expansion of the host range to monocotyledonous plants) will be analyzed in this review.

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Begomoviruses: what is the secret(s) of their success?: Trends in Plant Science (cell.com)
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To be seen or not to be seen: Latent infection by *tobamoviruses*

Tobamovirus, Latent infection, Symptoms, Diagnosis

Germany

This review looks at the group of *Tobamoviruses* to which tomato brown rugose fruit virus belongs.

Some *Tobamoviruses* cause latent infection in their hosts, which means that no obvious symptoms are visible. This has implications of diagnostics as multiple infections with latent and non-latent viruses may only focus on the symptom-inducing viruses. Furthermore, latent viruses may affect symptomology or replication of co-infecting viruses which may lead to more severe symptoms on host plants.

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<https://www.mdpi.com/2223-7747/11/16/2166>

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Eggsplorer: a rapid plant-insect resistance determination tool using an automated whitefly egg quantification algorithm

Insect egg quantification, Rapid phenotyping, whitefly, Deep learning, Plant insect resistance

Netherlands

BACKGROUND

Counting of insects on plants is crucial in plant breeding for insect resistance or for assessment of crop protection products. The traditional method of visually counting insects using a microscope is time-consuming. For instance, whiteflies can lay up to hundreds of eggs on a single leaf within a few days.

RESULTS

Researchers created a tool called **Eggsplorer**, which automates the counting of whitefly eggs. These images were used to train a deep learning model that can detect and count the eggs accurately. In testing, Eggsplorer achieved a counting accuracy of nearly 94% when compared to manual counts.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATION

Eggsplorer presents a new method for fast automatic determination of insects eggs on plants, that is easily accessible for users in a web-based application. Eggsplorer could be integrated into mobile phone platforms allowing users to collect data on the go and receive real-time advice on pest infestation.

»»» SABER MÁS

Eggsplorer: a rapid plant–insect resistance determination tool using an automated whitefly egg quantification algorithm | Plant Methods | Full Text (biomedcentral.com).

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Solanum elaeagnifolium and *S. rostratum* as potential hosts of the tomato rugose fruit virus

Solanum elaeagnifolium, *Solanum rostratum*, Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus (ToBRFV), Invasive weeds

Israel

Invasive weeds pose a significant threat to agriculture, causing notable crop yield and economic losses. They serve as reservoirs for viruses, notably the tomato brown rugose fruit virus (**ToBRFV**), which has overcome resistance alleles in cultivated tomato varieties, leading to severe crop damage. This study investigates the potential of invasive weed species, particularly *Solanum elaeagnifolium* and *S. rostratum*, as hosts for **ToBRFV** and a mild strain of pepino mosaic virus (**PepMV-IL**). Results show susceptibility of *S. elaeagnifolium* and *S. rostratum* to **ToBRFV**, with *S. rostratum* also susceptible to **PepMV-IL**. Mixed infections in *S. rostratum* and *S. nigrum* plants display viral synergism, exacerbating disease symptoms. Bioassay experiments demonstrate transmission of **ToBRFV** from infected weeds to tomato plants, particularly concerning due to the distribution and abundance of these weed species, which increase the risk of virus transmission.

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<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0282441>

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